

Investigating a Mixed Model of Graduate Statistic Course for Engineering Students

Meiqin Li¹

¹University of Virginia, 156 Engineer's Way, Charlottesville, VA 22904

Abstract

Guided by ASA guidelines for statistics education and informed by literature reviews and student needs, we adapted Kern's six-step approach to redesign the "Statistics for Engineers and Scientists" course, previously taught in a theory-based manner. The redesigned course, termed the Mixed Model that was not seen in literature yet, includes both in-person and virtual students in the same class meetings and incorporates mixed active learning elements. Our evaluation revealed that most students responded positively to the redesign, particularly appreciating the integration of R into daily work and in-class active learning activities. This paper compared the learning performance of in-person and virtual students within the same class meetings, a comparison not previously documented in existing literature. We found that virtual students required more time to complete the same tasks as in-person students. Additionally, graduate students perceived the coursework as excessive, despite it being reasonable (~10 hours per week), potentially raising important questions about how to align educational goals with students' perceptions of a reasonable workload in graduate course education.

Key Words: Graduate Statistics, Engineering Statistics, Mixed Model, in-person, virtual, Curriculum Redesign, Programming in R, Active Learning

1. Introduction

Statistics applies in engineering courses in various ways, including Experimental Design, Quality Control, Reliability Analysis, Modeling and Simulation, and Structural Analysis. Statistics plays a crucial role in various engineering disciplines by providing quantitative tools for decision-making, problem-solving, and data-driven analysis.

At our institution, APMA/MAE 6430-Statistics for Engineers and Scientists is a course targeting graduate students in the engineering school to equip them with prerequisite statistical techniques for other engineering curricula and applications. This course was taught by a senior professor (who now retired) for decades in the old fashion way till one of my former colleagues who converted some examples and homework problems in programming setting. When the research group of this paper took over this course two years ago, we found that there are many spaces to improve the curriculum design, and this paper investigates the effectiveness of the redesign for the first iteration that happened in Spring 2024. We expect that we will continue to improve the curriculum design for more iterations in the future based on the findings.

How to redesign a course is a challenging and complex task. We adapted and modified the approach of Kern's six-step curriculum design (Thomas et al., 2015) as the guideline. Even Kern's six-step approach is widely used in Medicine field curriculum development, it is applicable for other fields with some modifications. The modified Kern's six-step approach we adapted is described as the following six steps. The first step involves assessing the current curriculum to determine if a relevant course exists. If not, proceed to step two. In step two, clearly articulate and define the vision and goals for the curriculum. The third step involves carefully selecting appropriate content and resources. Moving on to the fourth step, strategically design instructional strategies and engaging activities aligned with the defined goals. The fifth step is to initiate the implementation of the curriculum, followed by a comprehensive evaluation to assess the effectiveness of the changes

made. All steps required careful and thoughtful investigation and examination such as literature reviewing, students' background checking, major needs, etc. These six steps collectively guide the process of curriculum development. This modification was successfully applied to outside of Medicine field. For example, the authors in (M. Li, 2023) utilized this approach to revamp a Linear Algebra course for engineering students by incorporating numerical components by using MATLAB as a tool and dominant majority of students reflected positively for this redesign when evaluating its effectiveness (M. Li & Taggart, 2024).

Guided by American Statistical Association (ASA)'s guidelines (most updated 2014) for statistic education along with reviewing literature, and investigating the composition of students, the course was redesigned in a mixed way called Mixed Model by modifying Kern's six-step curriculum design approach (Thomas et al., 2015). Since this course is a standard course with standard coverage of content, we skipped Step 1 and Step 3, that means, in term of content, we cover almost the same topics as before, such as Confidence Intervals, Hypotheses testing, ANOVA, Regression, Classification, Tree models, Unsupervised Learning, and Categorical Data Analysis. In step two, like the most statistic educators, we defined the goal of the course to gain the ability to analyze and interpret data effectively by understanding key statistical concepts and methods, allowing students to draw meaningful conclusions from data sets, identify patterns, and make informed decisions and predictions based on evidence, especially in research and data-driven field. Consequently, when applying the modified Kern's approach, the focus for this project will be step4-6. We will introduce how to conduct Step 4 in the Class Format section below, and we implemented this redesign in Spring 2024 as the first iteration, which is step5. Then we conducted assessment of effectiveness for this first iteration's redesign at the end of semester, which is step 6, and is the focus of this paper.

Lots of studies on statistic education boomed in the last decades, with many focusing on undergraduate statistics and with the following critical ingredients: i)using real-world data and problems such as indicated in (Cui & Liu, 2021), ii) active learning of students such as (Kalaian & Kasim, 2014), iii) using software and simulation such as (Stemock & Kerns, 2019), iv)using statistics in laboratories and projects such as (Yensy et al., 2022), and v)early and frequent exposure to statistics such as (Sparks, 2017). In term of graduate statistics education, the literature is significant less even still much. For example, there are literature investigating strategies for teaching graduate statistics courses (McKim et al., 2019) and students' perception about online graduate statistics course (Jiang et al., 2019). And for graduate statistics education for engineering students, even less studies. The existing studies mostly focused on incorporating a certain form of statistic learning into engineering curricula (Zhan et al., 2009) and describe how they did it. But it was not seen yet in the literature that such a Mixed Model we used for engineering students being studied. This paper focuses on the assessment of such redesign by investigating students' perceptions on its effectiveness, namely, step 6 in the modified Kern's approach after describing the Mix Model.

2. Class Format – Mixed Model

The redesigned course was called a Mixed Model mainly because of the following three aspects.

2.1 Mixed student compositions

The course has mixed student compositions. This is a combination of three different sections. One section we call MAE is for in-person Mechanical and Aerospace graduate students. Another section we call VEO is a section composed of virtual students who belong to the Virginia Engineering Online Program, and these students are usually full-time working, but take this course as a required course to obtain VEO degree. Online VEO students have the same degree requirements and achieve the same ME degree as those who learn in person at our school. The third section we call APMA, with graduate students from different engineering majors and treat this course as applied mathematics course.

2.2 Mixed patterns

This course has mixed patterns: partially lecturing and partially flipped. Instructors met students from MAE section and APMA sections twice per week with 75 minutes for each class meeting in person in the same classroom at the same time. The instructor recorded all lecturing, so VEO students could watch the recordings in the flipped learning method.

2.3 Mixed ingredients with Mixed Pedagogies

We designed mixed instructional strategies and engaging activities (Kern's step 4) aligned with the defined goals. In this course, all students learn statistical techniques by solving real data driven problems in programming R throughout the semester via a mixed of ingredients.

See the table below for the description of the class components and instructional strategies with their description.

Table 1: Class components and pedagogies with their description

Ingredients and pedagogies	Description
reading	Students were advised to read the textbook materials a week in advance of the topics being taught.
pre work (PreWk)	Students were assigned PreWK most weeks to cover some core concepts they have read.
slides	Slides notes covering all key concepts are made available to students through the Canvas course site. The instructor uses these slides to teach both the concepts and related examples.
lecture/recording	During the first part of each class, the instructor lectured on the main topics and recorded the sessions so students—especially VEO students—could review them later
in-class group work (ClassWk)	We employ an active learning pedagogy in this course. The instructor designs in-class problems to engage students in collaborative learning. During the second half of each session, students work in groups to solve these problems, submitting one solution per group. If they are unable to complete the tasks during class time, they continue working together outside of class to finish them
after-class group homework (HW)	Throughout the semester, students completed a total of 10 homework assignments outside the classroom, working collaboratively in groups with one submission per group. Each assignment focused on core content recently covered in class, aiming to reinforce understanding and support material review."
seminar-like classes with presentations (Presentation)	Periodically, we implemented seminar-style learning sessions. The instructor distributed a task sheet for students to work on collaboratively. In groups, students explored the relevant concepts, engaged in peer discussions, and then presented their findings at the front of the class.
Final projects	The course includes a challenging and comprehensive final project focused on applying statistical techniques to solve real-world problems involving large-scale datasets.
group collaboration	Group collaboration is another key pedagogical approach we adopted in this course redesign. Students worked together on most tasks, fostering teamwork and shared learning
incorporating R into the daily course work,	R is integrated throughout the course—including lectures, PreWK, ClassWK, homework, presentations, and the final project—with the goal of enabling students to apply statistical techniques and implement solutions to real-world problems through programming.

3. Evaluate the Redesign

There are many ways to evaluate the redesign of a course. Research revealed that students' perceptions of innovative instruction and task orientation positively predict their academic achievement (Z. Li & Li, 2022), and we don't have the data from previous semesters, hence, we mainly focus on students' perceptions on such redesign along with artifacts to evaluate the Mixed Model.

3.1 Research Design

3.1.1 Research Questions

RQ1. To what extent do students perceive their data programming skills and statistical techniques improve over the redesigned semester? Is there any difference between the in-person and online group?

RQ2. To what extent do students perceive R as helpful in mastering statistical techniques? Is there any difference between the in-person and online group?

RQ3. How do students perceive the helpfulness of different course elements? Is there any difference between the in-person and online group?

3.1.2 Study Method

A total of 25 participants from APMA/MAE 6430 participated in this study. The main data sources are students' artifacts and end of semester survey designed targeting toward the above research questions that included open-ended questions to obtain qualitative data. To address RQ1, we examine students' assignment problem solving process, students' reports/presentations of projects, complemented by a survey with students' self-reported perceptions of improvements. To address RQ2 and RQ3, we mainly utilized the survey to gauge students' perceptions. We used a mixed method to analyze the data, namely, used statistic tools to analyze quantitative data, and used deductive method to analyze qualitative data.

3.2 Results

3.2.1 Results for RQ1: To what extent do students perceive their data programming skills and statistical techniques improve over the redesigned semester? Is there any difference between the in-person and online group? We used three sets of survey questions to investigate this research question.

Set 1: Please indicate the ease with which you can do the following in R

Table 2: Student's perceptions of their ability to use R (n=22)

Please indicate the ease with which you can do the following in R	Mean	SD	$H_0: \mu = 4$ vs $H_a: \mu > 4$		$H_0: \mu = 4.8$ vs $H_a: \mu > 4.8$	
			t value	p-value	t value	p value
Remember instructions and coding styles.	5.32	1.23	5.48	9.83e-06***	2.15	0.022**
Know the needed codes	5.14	1.17	4.57	8.34e-05***	1.35	0.095
Debug a program when the result is not what I want	4.77	1.86	1.93	0.033**	NA	NA

*** significant, $p < .005$, ** significant, $p < .05$, * significant, $p < .1$

1-with a lot of difficulty, 2-with difficulty, 3- with some difficulty, 4- neutral, 5-somewhat easily, 6-easily, 7-very easily

To draw statistically significant conclusions, the collected data was analyzed by hypothesis tests using two different null hypotheses (H_0) and alternative hypotheses (H_a) based on the mean score values. For instance, the null hypothesis $H_0: \mu = 4$ assumes that students have a neutral stance on the statement, while the alternative hypothesis $H_a: \mu > 4$ suggests that students tend to somewhat agree with the statement. The results of these hypothesis tests are presented in Table 2. For each question, since the sample size is not big enough, we apply one Sample t-test. This analysis shows students perceive their ability to use R as significantly high.

Set 2: Please indicate how overwhelmed you feel about the following:

Table 3: Student's perception of feeling overwhelmed using R (n=22)

Please indicate how overwhelmed you feel about the following	mean	SD	$H_0: \mu = 3$ vs $H_a: \mu < 3$	
			t-value	p-value
Programming in general.	1.86	1.13	-4.74	5.59e-05***
Programming in R.	2.14	1.04	-3.91	0.0004***
Solving a statistical problem in general.	1.91	1.02	-5.02	2.86e-05***
Solving a statistical problem using R.	2.23	0.87	-4.17	0.0002***
Designing and creating a tutorial.	2.36	1.18	-2.54	0.0096**
Designing and creating a tutorial in R	2.55	1.18	-1.80	0.043**

*** significant, $p < .005$, ** significant, $p < .05$, * significant, $p < .1$

1- Not at all overwhelmed, 2- Slightly overwhelmed, 3- Moderately overwhelmed,
4- Very overwhelmed, 5- Extremely overwhelmed

To draw statistically significant conclusions, the collected data was analyzed by hypothesis tests using various null hypotheses (H_0) and alternative hypotheses (H_a) based on the mean score values. For instance, the null hypothesis $H_0: \mu = 3$ assumes that students have a neutral stance on the statement, while the alternative hypothesis $H_a: \mu < 3$ suggests that students tend to somewhat agree with the statement. The results of these hypothesis tests are presented in Table 3. For each question, since the sample size is not big enough, we apply one Sample t-test. This analysis shows that they felt comfortable to solve statistical problems using R.

Set 3: Please indicate your agreement with the following statements about the usefulness of R as a general language.

We use “agree” to include “somewhat agree”, “agree” and “strongly agree”. Similarly, we use “disagree” to include “somewhat disagree”, “disagree” and “strongly disagree”. From the barplot in Figure 1 and the descriptive analysis in Table 4, Students perceived R to be useful in the future coursework and projects, but neutral in their career. By analyzing the open-ended questions in the survey, Students perceive R as a highly valuable tool for their future careers and research, emphasizing its accessibility, advanced statistical capabilities, and versatility across disciplines. They recognize its usefulness in analyzing complex datasets, such as those from semiconductor fabrication or lidar systems, and appreciate how it enhances scientific understanding through trend analysis and data exploration. Many students note that R offers more powerful features than tools typically used in their workplaces or taught in undergraduate courses, making it especially beneficial for tasks involving data manipulation, machine learning, and research-driven insights. Some students expressed reservations about using R in their future careers. One noted a preference for

Python over R, while another highlighted that their field rarely involves complex statistical analysis, making R unlikely to be useful in their organization. Additionally, a student shared that they do not intend to pursue a job where coding—regardless of the language—is a significant component.

Figure 1: Student's perceptions on the usefulness of R as a general language

Table 4: Student's perceptions on the usefulness of R as a general language (n=22)

Please indicate your agreement with the following statements	Mean	SD	agree	neutral	disagree	$H_0: \mu = 4$ vs $H_a: \mu > 4$	
						t value	p-value
R will be useful in my future coursework	4.68	2.06	12/22 (54.5%)	3/22 (13.6%)	7/22 (31.8%)	1.56	0.0673*
I can see myself doing a project in the future that utilizes R	4.91	1.82	15/22 (68.2%)	3/22 (13.6%)	4/22 (18.2%)	2.34	0.0147**
My future career will likely include work with R	3.95	2.10	8/22 (36.4%)	5/22 (22.7%)	9/22 (40.9%)	NA	NA
The experience in R will help me master a different program (e.g., Python, Java, etc.)	4.32	2.12	10/22 (45.5%)	5/22 (22.7%)	7/22 (31.8%)	0.70	0.245

*** significant, $p < .01$, ** significant, $p < .05$, * significant, $p < .1$

1-strongly disagree, 2-disagree, 3-somewhat disagree, 4-neutral, 5-somewhat agree, 6-agree, 7-strongly agree

Student artifacts such as homework, projects and exams also showed that students felt comfortable to use R to solve statistical problems. Independent t-test showed that there is no significant difference between the online students and in-person students on their perceptions of ability to use R and of the usefulness of R in their future course work or career.

3.2.2 Results for RQ2: To what extent do students perceive R as helpful in mastering statistical techniques? Is there any difference between the in-person and online group? We used a set of survey Likert questions along with open-ended questions to investigate this research question.

Table 5: Student's perceptions on the usefulness of R as a tool to learn Statistics (n=22).

Please indicate your agreement with the statements about the usefulness of R in a statistic class	Mean	sd	agree	neutral	disagree	$H_0: \mu = 5$ vs $H_a: \mu > 5$	
						t value	p value
R will help me manage statistic projects	5.95	0.95	19/22 (86.4%)	3/22 (13.6%)	0/22 (0%)	4.71	5.91e-05***
R will help me answer statistic questions that cannot be solved by hand	6.50	0.91	21/22 (95.5%)	0 (0%)	1/22 (4.5%)	7.71	7.45e-08***
R will help me master statistic concepts	5.73	1.32	19/22 (86.4%)	1/22 (4.5%)	2/22 (9.1%)	2.59	0.0085***
R will make learning statistic more efficient overall	5.95	1.25	20/22 (90.9%)	0 (0%)	2/22 (9.1%)	3.57	0.000895***

*** significant, $p < .005$, ** significant, $p < .05$, * significant, $p < .1$

1- strongly disagree, 2-disagree, 3- somewhat disagree, 4- neutral, 5-somewhat agree, 6-agree, 7- strongly agree

Figure 2: Student's perceptions on the usefulness of R as a tool to learn Statistics

The above analysis shows that students perceived R to be significantly helpful to master statistical techniques (Table 5).

By analyzing the open-ended questions in the survey, while there is student reflecting that “I feel that I spent more time wrestling with R than with actually learning to understand the underlying statistics concepts”, students widely perceive R as a valuable tool for learning statistics, emphasizing its practicality, efficiency, and relevance to real-world applications. Many appreciated how R allowed them to focus on statistical concepts without being overwhelmed by complex math, thanks to its readily available functions and robust capabilities. They found it especially helpful for solving problems quickly, exploring advanced topics like regression and bootstrapping, and tackling tasks that would be tedious or impractical by hand. Several students noted that R is commonly used in research and industry, making its inclusion in the course both timely and professionally beneficial. While some acknowledged challenges with coding, they still recognized R’s potential to deepen understanding and enhance statistical skill development.

Independent sample t-test showed that there is no significant difference between the online students and in-person students on their perceptions of the helpfulness of R to learn statistical techniques.

3.2.3 Results for RQ3: How do students perceive the helpfulness of different course elements? Is there any difference between the in-person and online group?

Figure 3: Students’ perceptions of different components

Table 6: Students’ perceptions of different components (removed those who did not use the resources)

	Daily R	Collaboration	Reading	PreWK	Slides	Lecture	ClassWK	HW	Project	Presentation
Mean	3.95	3.8	3.15	3.62	3.60	3.45	3.81	3.67	3.62	2.74
SD	0.92	1.36	1.04	1.28	0.99	1.10	1.12	0.91	1.24	1.45

1-not at all helpful, 2-slightly helpful, 3- moderately helpful, 4- very helpful, 5-extremely helpful

Students found most course components helpful, with their preferences reflecting a clear order of usefulness. Daily use of R was rated highest, followed by weekly class activities (ClassWK) and collaboration, which supported hands-on learning and peer engagement. Homework and pre-week materials were also seen as valuable for reinforcing concepts and preparing for class. Projects offered practical application, while slides and notes helped clarify key ideas. Lectures were helpful but ranked lower, and readings and seminar presentations were mentioned least, suggesting they were less central to students' learning experience.

When analyzing whether there is significant difference between the online and in-person students, we found that online students spent significantly more time to finish the same task to achieve similar performance.

Figure 4: Study time for different sections

Conclusion and Discussion

This study found that students significantly improved their R programming skills and statistical techniques through the redesigned course, which integrated R into daily activities and emphasized active learning. Most students responded positively to the structure, especially the hands-on coding and collaborative classwork, which were perceived as the most helpful components. However, some students—particularly graduate and virtual learners—reported that the workload was excessive, with repetitive assignments and a focus on managing R sometimes overshadowing the learning of statistical concepts. Virtual students also required more time to complete tasks compared to their in-person peers.

While most course elements were well-received, reading assignments and seminars were seen as less beneficial. These findings highlight the importance of aligning educational goals—such as fostering independent learning and real-world application of skills—with students' expectations of a reasonable workload, especially in graduate-level education. The limited class size presents a constraint on generalizability, but the insights gained offer valuable guidance for refining the curriculum and supporting other educators interested in adopting similar mixed instructional models. Future revisions will aim to streamline assignments, reduce redundancy, and better balance coding practice with conceptual understanding to enhance student learning outcomes.

References

- Cui, L., & Liu, Z. (2021). Synergy between research on ensemble perception, data visualization, and statistics education: A tutorial review. *Attention, Perception, and Psychophysics*, 83(3). <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13414-020-02212-x>
- <https://www.amstat.org/education>. (n.d.).
- Jiang, M., Ballenger, J., & Holt, W. (2019). Educational leadership doctoral students' perceptions of the effectiveness of instructional strategies and course design in a fully online graduate statistics course. *Online Learning Journal*, 23(4). <https://doi.org/10.24059/olj.v23i4.1568>
- Kalaian, S. A., & Kasim, R. M. (2014). A meta-analytic review of studies of the effectiveness of small-group learning methods on statistics achievement. *Journal of Statistics Education*, 22(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/10691898.2014.11889691>
- Li, M. (2023). Developing Active Learning of Linear Algebra in Engineering by Incorporating MATLAB and Autograder. ASEE Annual Conference and Exposition, Conference Proceedings.
- Li, M., & Taggart, J. (2024). Student Perceptions on the Effectiveness of Incorporating Numerical Computations into an Engineering Linear Algebra Course. 2024 ASEE Annual Conference & Exposition.
- Li, Z., & Li, B. (2022). A path analysis of university EFL students' perceptions of the classroom environment and academic achievement. *Global Journal of Foreign Language Teaching*, 12(3). <https://doi.org/10.18844/gjflt.v12i3.7418>
- McKim, C., Young, S., & Weatherford, J. (2019). Strategies for teaching graduate statistics courses: A qualitative study. *Educational Research: Theory and Practice*, 30(1).
- Sparks, S. D. (2017). Statistics Lessons Get New Look in Early Grades - Education Week. *Education Week*, 36(28).
- Stemock, B., & Kerns, L. (2019). Use of commercial and free software for teaching statistics. *Statistics Education Research Journal*, 18(2). <https://doi.org/10.52041/serj.v18i2.140>
- Thomas, P. A., Kern, D. E., Hughes, M. T., & Chen, B. Y. (2015). Curriculum development for medical education: A six-step approach. In *Curriculum Development for Medical Education: A Six-Step Approach, Third Edition*. <https://doi.org/10.3126/jmcjms.v12i02.69143>
- Yensy, N. A., Sasongko, R. N., Kristiawan, M., Apriyani, D., & Hidayatulloh, H. (2022). THE EFFECTIVENESS OF PROJECT-BASED LEARNING MODELS IN IMPROVING UNDERSTANDING OF STATISTICAL CONCEPTS. *AKSIOMA: Jurnal Program Studi Pendidikan Matematika*, 11(2). <https://doi.org/10.24127/ajpm.v11i2.5102>
- Zhan, W., Fink, R., & Fang, A. (2009). Teaching statistics to Electronics Engineering Technology students. ASEE Annual Conference and Exposition, Conference Proceedings.